
A Role of SMAK in Skill Education as A Leading Industrial Training Center (ITC) in The Era of Globalization

Rajendra Shankarrao Mogane

Research Student,

Dept. of Commerce and Management, Shivaji University, Kolhapur.

Corresponding Author – Rajendra Shankarrao Mogane

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15063676

Introduction:

SMAK is situated at Gokul Shirgoan MIDC, Kolhapur. Shirolu Manufacturer's Association (SMAK) has established training centre under the Basic Training Centre (BTC) scheme. The object behind establishing SMAK is to provide skilled work force to industries. Basic Training Center (BTC) was established in the year 1982 by the SMAK under the Apprenticeship act 1961. It is unique 'Group Training Scheme' in India which is run by SME industrial entrepreneurs. SMAK established Govt. Affiliated Industrial Training Institute (ITI) in 1994 to provide the skilled man power to industries. SMAK conducts a full range of academic activities in the field of vocational education covering training, teaching and skill development. SMAK ITI has fulfilled with advanced Welding Simulator machine, PLC trainer kit, Hydraulic & Pneumatic training machines.

Shirolu Manufacturer's Association (SMAK) is one of the leading organizations in Western Maharashtra with more than 1000 Entrepreneurs network located in Shirolu Industrial Estate, Kolhapur. SMAK is established to address the various industry-related problems of the entrepreneurs.

Smak and Globalization:

The role of SMAK in globalization is very important as the SMAK provides well-trained and skillful manpower to the global industries specially in Kolhapur industrial area. Kolhapur has been a major driving force in the foundry industry of India, well known globally. Pioneering the trends and innovatively leading the industry to new frontiers and avenues has been its major role. There are different SSI establishments in Shirolu industrial area like heavy to medium foundries (ferrous and nonferrous), forging units, hi-tech machine shops, fabrication and assembly units who are presently exporting to countries in Europe and USA. Shirolu Manufacturers Association (SMAK), Kolhapur has launched an ambitious project called SMAK Export Promotions (SEP) to encourage entrepreneurs in MIDC Shirolu Industrial Estate to increase their participation in International Trade by providing them with up-to-date information on Exports.

Mission of Smak:

The SMAK's Mission is opening Global opportunities for their motivated member companies and opening the market for their products. SMAK has already successfully completed the MSME lean cluster project two years ago and it is successfully operational. For this SEP

project the SMAK has formed a cluster of selected skilled export capable 20 MSME based companies based in MIDC Shirol engaged in Ferrous and Non-Ferrous Casting Manufacturing and Machining, Steel and Alloy Casting and Machining, Product and Fabrication.

Objective of the Study:

1. To know the total intake capacity of trainee students for different trades at SMAK
2. To evaluate student centric facilities available to the trainee students at SMAK
3. To review the opinion of the trainee students of SMAK about skills imparted
4. To identify the immediate job acquired by the trainee students after training at SMAK

Significance of the Study:

As far as the Indian Economy is concerned the technical and vocational training for skill enhancement among youth plays a significant role for the industrial development. The skill provided by SMAK to the trainees help to increase the productivity and improves skills of the youth which is needed to be employed in various industries. The training programme of SMAK focuses on the trainees that they are better equipped with the skill required for the industrial jobs. In the modern era of industrialization, the machinery and techniques of production are highly mechanized or automated. In such situation, the industries need to train their employees with the particular skill. The SMAK imparts high skills in youth to operate new machinery, new processes and new production techniques.

Statement of Research Problem:

SMAK is providing vocational as well as educational training through

various trades and specially designed courses for enhancement of industrial skills in students and to fulfill the training needs of various industries in Kolhapur region. The main problem before the training institutes is to evaluate the need of the industry and to design valid and efficient courses for different industries. The new machinery, new procedure, new mechanism and new production technique creates more challenges before the industries of skilled and trained workers. In this situation the SMAK plays important role with the fully equipped and full-fledged training mechanism and modern techniques for coordination and integration of such training courses. Hence the present study has been undertaken by the researcher titled as ‘**A role of SMAK in skill education as a leading Industrial Training Center (ITC) in the era of globalization**’

Research Methodology:

Research is the common parlance refers to the search for knowledge. The Research Design is conceptually structured within which the research is conducted. It constitutes the blue print for the collection, measurement and analysis of the data.

The present study is concerned with ‘**A role of SMAK in skill education as a leading Industrial Training Center (ITC) in the era of globalization**’. In this study, the present status of SMAK as regards to Intake for each trade, Skill imparted in different trades, and acquired jobs by trainees after training and other related aspects with skill enhancement has been investigated by the researcher.

Sources of Data Collection:

The present study will depend mainly on primary and secondary data. The researcher has adopted survey method and observation method for data collection. The relevant data has been collected from

SMAK in the form of primary and secondary needed for the study.

Primary Data -The primary sources are those from which the data are collected afresh, collected for the first time and happened to be original in character. In the present study the primary data related with the training practices such as intake for per trade, different skills imparted, student centric facilities, training outcomes etc. have been collected from SMAKs trainee students and principal through different the interviews, discussions and observation at the SMAK.

Secondary Data -The data already collected and available in published or unpublished form is called as Secondary Data. The researcher collected secondary data which is already present and merely collected from an already existing source at SMAK. The researcher has collected the secondary data from written and published sources of SMAK as relevant articles, internet, newspaper, books, manual and record books of SMAK, prospectus of SMAK etc.

Area of Study:

The trainee students for different trades enrolled in SMAK situated at Shirol MIDC Kolhapur.

Data Collection Tools-The well-structured questionnaire was circulated to the trainee students and the head of the SMAK training institution.

Universe-The total student enrolled for different under the Intertrial Training Institute for the trades Eelectrecian, Fitter, Draftsman Mechanical, Welder is trades are 140 which is considered to be the universe of the study

Sample Size-The researcher has selected 30 trainee students as the sample for the study on convenience method.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

In this section the data collected from primary and secondary sources have been analyzed and interpreted.

Types of Training Centre And Its Intake At Smak:

Table No. 1.1

Sr. No.	Type of Training Centre and trades	Intake Capacity
Basic Training Centre		
1	Electrician	20
2	Machinist	20
3	Fitter	20
Industrial Training Institute		
1	Electrician	40
2	Fitter	40
3	Draftsman Mechanical	20
4	Welder	40
Autonomous training centre		
1	CNC	25
2	VMC	25
3	AutoCAD	25

(Source: Manual of SMAK)

Figure No. 1.1

It is observed from the table no.1.1 that the SMAK has classified its trades under the different head for administrative purposes and running different courses for different industrial trades. Under the Basic Training Centre SMAK is running basic

needful industrial courses, Under the Industrial Training Centre the SMAK has 4 training courses which are equivalent to the ITIs operating in Maharashtra, Under the Autonomous Training Centre the SMAK is running courses of modern industries which are equipped with highly automotive machineries. It is noted that the most of the training trades have intake of 20 while some trades with intake capacity 40. The admission in the SMAK is on the basis of granted intake capacity and it follows merit-based admission system.

Opinion Related With Skill Imparted In Trainee Students

The data given in the table 1.2 shows the opinion about the skill imparted in the trainee students. It covers the statements related with the different skills that students obtained during the course time. (5.SA=Strongly Agree, 4.A=Agree, 3.N=Neutral, 2.D=Disagree, 1.SD=Strongly Disagree)

Table No. 1.2: Opinion related with skill imparted in trainee students:

Sr. No.	Statements	Stat	SA	A	N	D	SD	Total	Mean	SD
1	Training made to adapt particular skill	F	16	11	3	0	0	30	4.40	0.75
		P	53.33	36.67	10.00	0.00	0.00	100		
2	Training made to use skill effectively	F	13	15	2	0	0	30	4.34	0.68
		P	43.33	50.00	6.67	0.00	0.00	100		
3	Training increased self-managed abilities	F	10	17	2	1	0	30	4.15	0.78
		P	33.33	56.67	6.67	3.33	0.00	100		
4	Training increased communication skill	F	9	16	4	1	0	30	4.10	0.77
		P	30.00	53.33	13.33	3.33	0.00	100		
5	Training increased confidence level	F	9	19	2	0	0	30	4.15	0.70
		P	30.00	63.33	6.67	0.00	0.00	100		
6	Training developed personality in an efficient way	F	8	17	3	2	0	30	4.00	0.86
		P	26.67	56.67	10.00	6.67	0.00	100		
7	Training imparted problem-solving ability	F	4	19	5	2	0	30	3.80	0.79
		P	13.33	63.33	16.67	6.67	0.00	100		
8	Training made aware about accountability	F	13	13	2	2	0	30	4.21	0.88
		P	43.33	43.33	6.67	6.67	0.00	100		
9	Training made cautious about job responsibility	F	13	14	0	3	0	30	4.30	0.73
		P	43.33	46.67	0.00	10.00	0.00	100		
10	Training taught to save time, labour and money	F	16	14	0	0	0	30	4.51	0.58
		P	53.33	46.67	0.00	0.00	0.00	100		

(Source: Field Survey)

1. The mean score of the opinion related to the statement 'Training made me able to adapt particular skill required for the job' is 4.40. It indicates that most of the trainee students agree that they have adapted particular skill in the training.

2. The mean score of the opinion related to the statement 'Training made me able to use the skill very effectively' is 4.34. It denotes that largely the trainee students are agreed that training has helped them to use their skill effectively.

3. The mean score of the opinion related to the statement ‘Training increased self-managed abilities’ is 4.15. It shows that most of the trainee students agree that training has increased their self-managed abilities.
4. The mean score of the opinion related to the statement ‘Training increased a good communication skill in me’ is 4.10. It reveals that most of the students agree that training has increased their communication skill.
5. The mean score of the opinion related to the statement ‘Training increased my confidence level in doing job’ is 4.15. It displays that most of the students agree that training has increased their confidence level in doing job.
6. The mean score of the opinion related to the statement ‘Training developed my personality in more efficient way’ is 4.00. It denotes that most of the students agree that training has developed their personality in an efficient way.
7. The mean score of the opinion related to the statement ‘Training imparted in me problem-solving ability in any adverse situation’ is 3.80. It denotes that largely the trainee students agree that training has enhanced their problem-solving skill.
8. The mean score of the opinion related to the statement ‘Training made me aware about accountability towards particular work’ is 4.21. It denotes that most of the trainee students that training made them aware about accountability.
9. The mean score of the opinion related to the statement ‘Training also made me cautious about responsibility towards job’ is 4.30. It denotes that mostly the trainee students agree that the training has made them cautious about the job responsibility.
10. The mean score of the opinion related to the statement ‘Training taught me how to save time, labour, money in conducting any job-related act.’ is 4.51. It denotes that largely agree that training has taught me how to save time, labour and money.

Table No. 1.3: Trainees acquired immediate jobs after training

Sr. No	Passing Year	Admissions	Acquired Immediate Jobs	Percentage
1	A.Y. 2018-19	118	103	87.28
2	A.Y. 2019-20	99	81	81.81
3	A.Y. 2020-21	71	64	90.14
4	A.Y. 2021-22	120	109	90.83
	Total	408	357	87.50

Figure No.1.2: Trainees acquired immediate jobs after training

It is observed from the table 1.3 and figure 1.2 that the 87.28 percent trainees acquired jobs in the year 2018-19, 81.81 percent trainees acquired jobs in the year 2019-20, 90.14 percent trainees acquired jobs in the year 2020-21 and 90.83 percent trainees acquired jobs in the year 2021-22. It is also noted that on an average 87.50 percent trainees have been employed in several industries immediate after training.

It is concluded that good number trainees of SMAK have obtained jobs immediate after the training. It reveals that the SMAK students have an excellent employability rate and job opportunities. It is noted that the almost on an average 87.50 percent is the employability rate which is better and it identifies that the SMAK provides highly skilled manpower to the industries and builds a better career of youth.

Findings, Suggestions and Conclusion:

Findings:

It is found from the opinion of the trainee students that most of the trainees are agree with several statements related with skill imparted and trainees that self-managed abilities, communication skill, confidence level, problem-solving abilities, aware of accountabilities are increased due to the training programme.

Suggestions:

The SMAK need to introduce some new courses needed in field of commerce with the new age of globalization. The new courses of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and modern automation industry need highly skilled and self-motivated employees which can be fulfilled by the

SMAK as the SMAK has already a good infrastructure with a successful trainee.

Conclusion:

It is concluded that good number trainees of SMAK have got jobs immediate after the training. It also reveals that the SMAK students have an excellent employability rate and job opportunities. It is noted that the trainee students of SMAK acquired many skills in a training programme which makes them well equipped with several skills required in the job market specially in the industrial sector.

References:

1. Prospectus, Manuals and Brouchers of SMAK
2. DVET Training Manual (2007-08), Mumbai.Pp.2
3. FICCI, (2010), Report on the skill development landscape, India Pp.25-26
4. Directorate of Vocational Education and Training, Manual, Government of Maharashtra, P.46
5. C.R.Kothari, (2004), Research Methodology- Methods and Techniques (second revised edition), New Age International (P) Limited.
6. <https://www.careerindia.com> › Colleges › Industrial Training Institute, Kolhapur
7. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Industrial_training_institute
8. <https://admission.dvet.gov.in>
9. <https://skilltraining.tn.gov.in/D/ET/>
10. <https://nsdcindia.org/>